

Informational Entropy and Specific Information Losing Constraints

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There seems to be examples in the literature of a single particle (said to represent an ideal gas) in a container of size V , which is then halved to $V/2$ without work being done, giving the idea of entropy spontaneously decreasing (1).

In previous notes (2), we have argued that a single particle with constant speed v in a box may be analyzed in terms of the ideal gas law and Sackur-Tetrode if information is “lost” through the creation of an average pressure expression. This loss of information gives rise to entropy and the amount of information lost (i.e the size of the box) determines the entropy, which is spatial in this case. In other words, if one begins with a deterministic situation and then imposes a constraint V , one is a priori yielding information (number of states) proportional to V . If one imposes a constraint $V/2$, one a priori yields less information (fewer states of the same size) and so has a smaller entropy. Thus, in this example, it seems that one may create entropy based on the information one is willing to yield, but this is linked to a physical constraint, namely the size of a container.

As noted above, we argue that beginning with the knowledge of a deterministic particle with constant speed v , giving up knowledge yields a statistical description with an inherent loss of knowledge linked to V (or L in one dimension). In such a case, one cannot return to the state of knowledge without erasing information entropy. For example, if a coin is tossed, one has entropy, but as soon as a measurement is done, entropy is 0. Likewise, if one has a 1-D container of length L and one inserts a partition in the middle, the statistical treatment of this problem would be to assume a gas at the same temperature on each side of the partition and we show, using the Sackur-Tetrode equation, that there is no change in entropy. To argue that after inserting a partition, one has a single particle on one side or the other really means returning to a deterministic picture (erasing entropy) and then assigning a new constraint which creates a different spatial entropy. Hence, one does not spontaneously decrease entropy. By knowing that the particle is in one side or the other is in a sense a measurement which means that there is not a spontaneous change in entropy, we argue.

Information Entropy

Information entropy is linked to a loss of information. If one has a coin lying on a table and one does not know which side is up, then there is Shannon’s entropy:

$$\ln(2) \quad ((1))$$

A measurement determines which side is facing up and erases this entropy, i.e. sets it to 0. Thus, entropy can be erased by a measurement and also created by an interaction, i.e. tossing a coin after one has determined which side was facing up. The interaction is associated with a built-in constraint that the coin can only be lying with one side face up (and only has two faces). In some physical problems, however, an interaction may be variable and so one may create a variable amount of entropy.

A Deterministic Particle

Consider a deterministic particle with constant speed v starting at $x=0$, $t=0$. As it moves to the right, one may place walls at $x=0$ and $x=L$. The particle will elastically bounce off the walls and be trapped, but everything is deterministic. One may now opt to remove deterministic measurements of t . In such a case, one no longer knows the position of the particle because $x=vt$. One has given up a certain amount of spatial information linked to L . The Shannon's entropy is:

$$\ln(L) \quad (\text{or } \ln(V) \text{ in 3-D}) \quad ((2))$$

One may note that this spatial informational information ((2)) appears in the Sackur-Tetrode equation and so informational entropy may be linked with thermodynamic entropy.

If instead of choosing L , one chose $2L$, ((2)) would become: $\ln(2L)$ ((3))

No extra work is done creating ((3)). Furthermore, choosing $L/2$, yields $\ln(L/2)$, which represents less entropy than ((2)). In all cases, one changes from an entropy=0 case, to a fixed entropy one based on the information one is willing to give up, which in turn is linked to box length.

As noted in (2), if one gives up this L information and introduces the idea of pressure (as existing at all times), then one may use the ideal gas law $PL = kT$ (where $T = mv^2$), $E = .5 T$ and the Sackur-Tetrode 1-D equation. In other words, giving up information leads to a statistical description regardless of whether the underlying system is probabilistic or deterministic, at least in this example.

The Case of a Partition

We now consider the above example with L . We argue that if one considers the particle as deterministic, one has measurements of $x=vt$ to prove this view. If one considers it as probabilistic, then one does not even know that there is one particle in the box of size L . There is simply a temperature and pressure as well as length L .

In such a statistical case, inserting a partition at $L/2$ means that one should assume that half the particles are on one side of the partition, and the other half on the other side. Then, pressure does not change because:

$$PL = NkT \text{ becomes } P L/2 = N/2 kT \text{ for each side} \quad ((3))$$

Furthermore, the initial entropy is:

$$S(\text{initial}) = N \text{ constant}_1 + \ln(N/L) + 3/2 \ln(U/L) \quad ((4a))$$

The entropy in each side is:

$$S(\text{side}) = N/2 \text{ constant } 1 + \ln((N/2)/(L/2)) + 3/2 \ln(N/2 kT/ (L/2)) \quad ((4b))$$

Thus, the total entropy is unchanged in the statistical view.

If one tries to argue that one has a single particle and that it is now on one side or the other is equivalent to:

- (A) Erasing the initial L based entropy and returning to the deterministic viewpoint
- (B) Changing from a deterministic viewpoint to an entropy based on L/2

Adding information, presumably through measurement, and then erasing it by imposing a different constraint is not a spontaneous process, and so we argue that one cannot state that:

Entropy spontaneously decreases in the above example. ((5))

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that entropy is linked to missing information. If one makes a measurement, (such as on a flipped coin), one may erase entropy. Alternatively, one may flip the coin and create entropy based on the particular constraints present (2 sides to a coin and a coin must lie on one face of the other). We suggest that there are scenarios for which one has variable constraints which give rise to different entropies when one erases information. We also suggest that one may have a situation with entropy (due to removed information) based on a parameter L (the size of box) and one may try to argue that one may spontaneously change this information removed to L/2, hence spontaneously decreasing entropy. We argue that it seems that one is really first adding information to the L system to remove its entropy and then introducing a new constraint, L/2. This is not a spontaneous process, and so we argue that one cannot state that entropy spontaneously decreases. We use the example of a deterministic particle in a 1-D box of size L as an example.

References

1. Pal, P.S. and Jayanavar, A.M. Maxwell's Demon, Szilard Engine and Landauer Principle (2016 or later) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1904.05256>
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